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INDICATORS OF SOME COMPONENTS OF THE METABOLIC SYNDROME IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE

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Annotation Seventy-three women and forty-six men with chronic kidney disease aged 20-69 years were examined. They studied the average blood pressure levels, body weight, waist circumference, and immunoreactive insulin. During the study, modern methods of examination and diagnostic criteria recommended for identifying the components of the metabolic syndrome were used. It was found that the average levels of the studied components of the metabolic syndrome in women are higher than in men. At the same time, it is shown that the average levels of all studied indicators are higher than the generally accepted reference values. The results of the work indicate the expediency of early detection and correction of the main components of metabolic c syndrome to prevent and treat chronic kidney disease.

Keywords: chronic kidney disease, blood pressure, body weight, waist circumference, insulin resistance.

Introduction

Over the past 20 years, chronic kidney disease (CKD) has become one of the most important factors affecting the health and mortality of the population [1,2,3]. Currently, in most countries of the world, the prevalence of CKD among the population is more than 10% [4]. An increase in the frequency of CKD is associated with diseases such as glomerulonephritis and other kidney diseases, diabetes mellitus, hypertension, atherosclerosis and others [5,6]. At the same time, the role of various metabolic disorders is shown [7,8]. The association of CKD with disorders of carbohydrate and lipid metabolism, as well as with comorbid diseases,

was revealed [9,10,11]. One of the most effective and economical methods of combating CKD is primary and secondary prevention of this disease among the population. To do this, it is necessary to have information about risk factors and their population values. At the same time, women's health should be given special importance because the differences in the female body make their own adjustments to the formation and course of a number of diseases and risk factors [12,13].

The purpose of the study is to study blood pressure, body weight, and insulin resistance levels among men and women with chronic kidney disease.

Material and methods.

One hundred nineteen patients suffering from CKD aged from 20 to 69 years were examined. The study did not include people with exacerbations of chronic diseases of the gastrointestinal tract, severe diseases of the cardiovascular system and endocrine system, as well as patients with stage 5 CKD.

Methods of studying the main components of the metabolic syndrome: - when assessing blood pressure (BP), the average values of systolic blood pressure (SAD) and diastolic blood pressure (DAD) were taken into account; - body weight was estimated by the Quetelet index (IQ), which was calculated according to the following formula: weight (kg)/ height (m)²; - the content of glucose was studied in venous blood on an empty stomach (after fasting > 12 hours). The levels of glycosylated haemoglobin (HbA1c), immunoreactive insulin, and the NOME index were also studied.

In the detection of CKD, the KDIGO criteria were used: a) the presence of one of the following criteria in the patient for more than three months - albuminuria ≥ 30 mg/day, abnormal urine sediment, electrolyte abnormalities in the defeat of the tubules, structural abnormalities during visualization; b) the glomerular filtration rate (GFR) < 60 ml/min / 1.73 m² for \geq three months regardless of the presence of signs of kidney damage. The glomerular filtration rate was calculated using two formulas: a) according to the Cockcroft-Gault formula based on creatinine clearance

(Cc) = $88 \times (140 - \text{age, years}) \times \text{body weight, kg} / 72 \times \text{serum creatinine, mmol/L.}$; b) according to the Cockcroft-Gault formula) / 1.73 m² (reduced to the normal surface of the body).

Statistical processing of the obtained data was carried out using the MedCalc software (<https://www.medcalc.org>) [14].

Results and discussion

The data obtained indicate that there are some differences between blood pressure in men and women suffering from CKD (Table. 1). The average levels of SAD in women were higher than in men. At the same time, the indicators of DAD in men and women were practically the same. These results may indicate that impaired filtration function of the kidneys can significantly affect blood pressure levels. At the same time, the indicators of SAD and DAD levels among men and women with CKD differ slightly from the values of these indicators in the general population.

Table 1.

Blood pressure indicators in patients of different genders suffering from chronic kidney diseases.

Indicators of statistical processing	Systolic blood pressures		Diastolic blood pressure	
	women	men	women	men
N	73	46	73	46
Average	139,130	134,565	86,957	86,304
Median	140,000	130,000	90,000	90,000
Variance	231,5857	318,6957	65,6010	99,3720
SD	15,2179	17,8520	8,0994	9,9685
RSD	0,1094	0,1327	0,09314	0,1155
SEM	1,8320	2,6321	0,9751	1,4698

Shapiro-Wilk	<0,0001	0,0011	<0,0001	<0,0001
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Note: Blood pressure readings are presented in mmHg.

It should also be noted that according to the criteria of the American College of Cardiology (ACC) and the American Heart Association (AHA), the average levels of SAD and DAD in women and men were higher than normal blood pressure values [15]. According to the ACC/AHA recommendation, SAD/DAD levels >130/85 mmHg refer to arterial hypertension and need treatment. At the same time, according to the ESC/ESH criteria, blood pressure indicators SAD/DAD >130/85 mmHg but <140/90 mmHg belong to the category of high normal blood pressure [15]. However, ESC/ESH still recommends antihypertensive therapy for blood pressure values above 130/85 mmHg in patients with CKD. Therefore, the average blood pressure levels in the studied group, considering the recommendations of both ACC/AHA and ESC/ESH, should be assessed as pathological and appropriate therapeutic measures should be carried out among them.

Next, the indicators of body weight and abdominal obesity were studied (Table 2). According to the data obtained, the average values of the Quetelet index among women with CKD were slightly higher than in men. The study results indicate that in men and women with CKD, the average Quetelet index values meet the criteria of overweight.

Waist circumference characterizes the presence and degree of abdominal obesity. According to the criteria of the International Diabetes Federation (IDF, 2005), abdominal obesity is assumed to have values greater than 82 cm for women and 94 cm for men. The average waist circumference in women was much higher (98,262 cm), than the standard criteria. In men, this indicator was within normal values (87,222 cm.). The data obtained indicate that abdominal obesity is more characteristic for women than men.

Table 2.

Average levels of the Quetelet index and waist circumference in women and men suffering from chronic kidney disease.

Indicators of statistical processing	Quetelet Index		Waist circumference (in cm.)	
	women	men	women	men
N	73	46	73	46
Average	27,780	25,418	98,262	87,222
Median	28,395	25,937	101,000	83,000
Variance	18,9889	11,7369	379,9269	147,4009
SD	4,3576	3,4259	19,4917	12,1409
RSD	0,1569	0,1348	0,1984	0,1392
SEM	0,5100	0,5051	2,2813	1,7901
Shapiro-Wilk criterion	0,0015	0,0773	<0,0001	0,1349

One of the main components of the metabolic syndrome is insulin resistance. In this regard, the average levels of immunoreactive insulin (IRI) and the NOME index were studied among patients with CKD (Table 3). It turned out that the average IRI of women was 1.4 times higher than that of men. At the same time, the average levels of ITI in women with CKD were at the level of the upper values of possible fluctuations in this indicator (23,837). Average values of the insulin resistance index (NOME index) in women were 1.8 times higher than in men. At the same time, the NOME index was 2.7 times higher for women and 1.5 times higher for men than the normal values of this indicator. It follows from the presented data that women with CKD are more susceptible to hyperinsulinemia and insulin resistance.

Table 3

Average levels of immunoreactive insulin and the NOME index among patients
 with chronic kidney disease

Indicators of statistical processing	Immunoreactive insulin (mked/ml)		HOMA Index	
	women	men	women	men
N	73	46	73	46
Average	23,837	17,060	7,419	4,075
Median	21,400	11,000	3,467	1,858
Variance	312,0816	139,4386	68,7386	21,2239
SD	17,6658	11,8084	8,2909	4,6069
RSD	0,7411	0,6922	1,1175	1,1306
SEM	2,0399	1,8221	0,9573	0,7109
Shapiro-Wilk criterion	<0,0001	0,0004	<0,0001	<0,0001

Conclusions

1. Blood pressure levels among patients with chronic kidney disease exceed typical values. At the same time, women have higher systolic blood pressure levels than men.
2. Men and women with chronic kidney disease have an increased body weight, which is more pronounced in women. At the same time, abdominal obesity is typical for women with chronic kidney disease, and abdominal obesity is not specific for men with this disease.
3. Men and women suffering from chronic kidney disease are characterized by hyperinsulinemia and insulin resistance. These indicators are more pronounced in women than in men.

4. For timely diagnosis, prevention and treatment of chronic kidney disease, blood pressure levels of body weight and insulin resistance should be detected and adjusted in a timely manner.

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